

Coordination behavior of baclofen towards cobalt(II) ion

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The complex of Co^{II} with baclofen has been prepared. The metal-ligand interaction in water medium has been studied polarographically at 25° and at an ionic strength of $\mu = 1.0 M$ KCl. The reduction of the complex at DME was found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. The analytical results indicate a 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry for Co^{II}-baclofen complex. The analgesic study reveals that the complex is more potent compared to the parent drug.

In continuation of our previous work¹, the present work has been designed to study the complex of Co^{II} with analgesic drug baclofen [4-amino-3-*p*-chlorophenylbutyric acid]² (1). The qualitative analysis of baclofen and its bioinorganic studies with Co^{II} has been done using polarography and amperometry. In addition, analgesic behavior of baclofen and its Co^{II} complex have also been studied.

(1)

Results and Discussion

Polarographic study of M : L complexation equilibrium : Co^{II} and its complex with baclofen ligand were found to be reversibly reduced in 0.1 M KCl at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 involving two electrons, which was evidenced by the plot of log *i* (*i*_d - *i*) vs *E*. The reduction was found to be diffusion-controlled, which was evidenced by *i*_d vs $\sqrt{t_{\text{cor}}}$ plot. On gradual increase of baclofen concentration, the half-wave potential of Co^{II} ion shifted to more electronegative values and the diffusion current also decreased, thereby showing complex formation between Co^{II} with baclofen.

The plots of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ (shift in the $E_{1/2}$) = ($E_{1/2}$)_c - ($E_{1/2}$)₀, against log *C*_x (logarithm of the concentration of the ligand) were linear showing the formation of single complex species in solution. Ligands³ method was therefore applied, which showed 1 : 1 (M : L) complex formation with formation constant, log $\beta_1 = 3.2$.

Amperometric determination of baclofen with Co^{II} : Co^{II} gave a well-defined polarographic wave in 0.1 M KCl at pH 5.0 ± 0.1. The diffusion current was found to be proportion-

al to its concentration. The baclofen did not produce any wave under the experimental conditions. The plateau potential for the polarographic wave of Co^{II}, i.e. -1.4 V vs SCE, was applied for carrying out amperometric titration. Co^{II} was taken as the titrate and the drug solution as titrant. The current-volume plots resulted in L-shaped curve. The endpoint as located by graphical method, revealed metal-to-drug ratio of 1 : 1, which corroborates the findings using polarographic method.

The analytical data also revealed 1 : 1 metal-drug ratio in the complex, which supports the finding using polarographic and amperometric methods.

IR spectral analysis of Co^{II}-baclofen complex : A critical comparison of the IR spectra of baclofen and its complex shows that the broad ligand band at 3200-3400 cm⁻¹ (N-H) appeared as a reduced and broad band⁴ at 3100-3300 cm⁻¹ and a new broad band appeared at 1650 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of Co^{II}-baclofen complex. This way due to the involvement of COOH group in composition. These observations indicate the involvement of nitrogen of N-H group and oxygen of carboxylic group in complex formation. However, band due to C-Cl stretching vibration at 730 cm⁻¹ remained at the same position in the spectra of both baclofen and its Co^{II}-complex.

Analgesic activity : Analgesic activity of baclofen and its complex was studied on the rat groups⁵. It was observed that the tail flick time without administration of baclofen drug or its Co^{II} complex is 6.8 s where as on administration of 20 mg/kg of the drug (baclofen) the tail-flick time increases from 7.0 to 14.7 after 0.0 min to 90.0 min after administering the drug to the rats. But if the observation is made after 120 min after administering the drug the tail-

Note

flick time decreases to 10.6 s, indicating that the effect of the drug decreased after 120 min of its administration. However, increased effect is observed by administering 20 mg/kg the Co^{II}-baclofen complex, where the tail-flick time increased to 16.7 s after 60.0 min of administering the complex. But it lost its effectiveness with due course of time. The activity was found to be in the order : baclofen < Co^{II}-baclofen complex.

Conclusion : On the basis of the polarographic/ amperometric studies of Co^{II}-baclofen complex and its analgesic activity against the rats, it could be concluded that the complex is more potent as compared to pure drug.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The drug, baclofen (Novartis Pharma AG, Basel) was used. Double-distilled water used as solvent.

Polarographic measurements were made on an Elico CL-357 DC-polarograph using dropping mercury electrode (DME) as a working electrode, a coiled platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as a reference electrode. Experimental sets were prepared by keeping overall Co^{II} (metal ion) and KCl (supporting electrolyte) concentrations fixed at 1.0 mM and 0.1 M, respectively. The ligand concentration was varied from 0.0 to 15 mM. The pH of the test solutions was adjusted to 5.0 ± 0.1 using HCl/NaOH solution.

The amperometric titrations were performed on a manually operated setup, equipped with a polyflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1×10^{-9} A/div) and an AJCO vernier potentiometer. DME was used as an indicator electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. The capillary characteristics of the DME were : $m^{2/3}, t^{1/6} = 2.5 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60 cm effective height of mercury column. The pH of the test solution was measured on a Systronics 335 pH meter.

For amperometric titrations, each experimental set

having different but known amount of the Co^{II} was prepared in appropriate quantity of supporting electrolyte (KCl) at pH 5.0 ± 0.1 and titrated separately against the standard solution of baclofen whose pH was also adjusted as that of the titrate (5.0 ± 0.1). The current after each addition of the titrant was read and a curve plotted, current against volume of titrant added.

Synthesis of complex : Cobalt chloride and baclofen (drug) solutions prepared separately in distilled water were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting solid complex was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at low temperature and stored over P₄O₁₀.

C, H, N and Cl were analyzed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The complexometric method was used for the estimation of cobalt⁶. The complex gave satisfactory elemental analyses. IR spectrum (KBr) was recorded on a Shimadzu 470 spectrophotometer.

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